

Drivers of and counterfactuals for the final energy and electricity consumption in EU industry

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1. Introduction

Energy demand is essential when planning for infrastructure and grid investment (Tadahiro N., Shigeyuki H., 2010). In order to properly model the demand-side of the energy market, several approaches have been proposed as to the selection of the independent and explanatory variables or features, as they are called in the AI literature. The approaches are indeed vast and ever-expanding. In this paper, we develop linear regression models for the forecasting of final energy and electricity for the industrial sector in six EU countries (Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, Portugal, and Greece). The aim of the investigation is twofold: first, to highlight the key drivers of these two types of energy consumption; and second, to introduce the potential of what-if counterfactual analysis on the selected features.

To this extent, various explanatory variables have been used and are discussed below as to their ability to inform our two types of industrial consumption.

2. Data sourcing

We clustered the socioeconomic features pertinent to our forecasting tasks in three feature categories: *size*, *price*, and *use efficiency*. As regards size, we experimented with an industrial production index, which shows the growth rate of industrial activity as well as with the value-added of the industrial activity (MEuro). Data for these indicators were sourced from the

Odyssee service (Odyssee-Mure, n.d.). The same source provided EU-wide data for final consumption (Mtoe) and electricity (Mtoe) of industry.

As regards pricing data, we used the price of gas and electricity with or without taxes and levies. All this data was found at and sourced from Eurostat (Energy Database, n.d.).

Finally, efficiency is, in the case of industry, driven principally by technological development. An important aspect of industrial consumption is that there is no reason for rebounding effects which are well known to occur in residential contexts (Sun J.H., 2001). Odyssee-Mure has developed an elaborate energy efficiency indicator (Odyssee-Mure, n.d.) called ODEX. For each industrial sector, the index is calculated as a weighted average of sub-sectoral indices of energy efficiency progress. A weighted average index is calculated on the basis of the share of each end-use/sub-sector in the sector's energy consumption. Interestingly, the indicator has not remained a theoretical construct but has been calculated and validated in all EU states using 1990 as a baseline.

The above data were in principle available from 1990 until 2019, although in some cases the data were available as far back as 1985.

The data used, as well as the statistical analysis to which they were subjected, have been publicly shared and can be found online at the OSF (Open Science Foundation, www.osf.io), and are fully accessible under the public project "JASP analysis of non-household (industrial) final energy and electricity consumption in the EU" (<https://osf.io/tw5qk>). The analyses can be seen directly at this location. Access to the raw data will require the files to be first downloaded and then opened in JASP.

Our investigation sought to provide insight into the following aspects of industrial final energy and electricity consumption.

1. Which indicator of size, the value-added of the industrial activity or the production index, is a better predictor of consumption?
2. Do we have tangible evidence that energy efficiency as modelled via ODEX affects consumption?
3. Is price a driver of industrial consumption?

Arguably, both energy efficiency and price can be affected by short- to mid-term policies.

3. Results

Various feature combinations were tested. We eliminated combinations where counter-intuitive coefficients showed up in the regression equation. Such is the case with, for example, a price

with a positive coefficient signalling that a price increase would lead to an increase in consumption. Additionally, a further important consideration was to retain only features that entered the equations with a low p-value, signalling a good statistical significance of it. Also, features that upon inclusion displayed high collinearity as reported by the SVI indicator were excluded. Collinearity means that the introduction of a new feature does not introduce independent information.

In terms of accuracy, out of the twelve cases, in seven cases the linear regression models were of a good accuracy with a value of an adjusted R² between 0.8 and 0.95. Four cases were of lower accuracy and an adjusted R² between 0.5 and 0.65, while in the case of Germany (final consumption) no model emerged. A possible reason for this is that in the '90s and during the integration of the Eastern regions of the country, Germany experienced a rare transition period whose socioeconomic characteristics were fluid and very particular to the moment.

Clearly, higher model accuracies would require closer attention to every specific socioeconomic environment. However, we can be confident about some of the findings as they occurred persistently in all cases investigated. We would summarise these as follows:

The energy efficiency indicator is a key driver of final and electric consumption. It showed up in five out of five (as Germany was not included) cases of final consumption and two cases of electricity consumption.

Prices, either in their net form, or inclusive of taxes and levies, did not show up at all. Thus, one can conclude that the demand is rather inelastic to prices. Price elasticity of demand has been investigated (JBF, 2003), although the evidence is rather conflicting. In Japan (Nan Wang, Gento Mogi, 2017), the price elasticity of electricity demand was found to be significant, a conclusion opposing previous approaches in the country, such as that of the Japan Business Federation (JBF) in 2003, which claimed that price elasticity of energy demand is low and that therefore carbon tax cannot suppress carbon emissions (JBF, 2003, as cited in Keibun Mori, 2012). Environmental taxation has also been scrutinised in the EU (EEA, 2016), although no assessment of its impact on demand has been attempted. Our work here contributes to this discussion; we focus on the industrial demand alone. There is significant evidence that within this scope demand is truly inelastic to price.

As regards “size” indicators, the industrial production index appeared to perform somewhat better when compared to the value-added of the industry.

A similar neural network analysis is currently ongoing, exclusively on the features that the statistical analysis has revealed as pertinent.

4. A vision for counterfactual based decision support

An important decision that could be supported by means of the above investigations would be:

“What is the best action that I should take in order to achieve an x% reduction of greenhouse emissions in the mid-term horizon?”

Such questions are typically addressed using counterfactual analysis. A counterfactual explanation of a prediction describes the smallest change to the feature values that changes the prediction to a predefined output. Counterfactual analysis is also referred to as local interpretability in the sense that it does not aim to propose a general surrogate and more transparent model in the place of the typical black box of the neural network. Instead, it aims at addressing “what if” type questions and finding the minimal tweak of the model features that could secure this new goal.

If we are to realistically tweak model features to perform “what if” analyses, it is critical to identify the actionable features. One cannot possibly, in the short- to mid-term, change the production index. Efficiency, however, can be actionable in the form of policies that support the introduction of energy-efficient production equipment. Similarly, energy prices/taxes are in principle actionable, although in our investigation they did not show up in the regression equations.

In view of the energy transition and the growing pressure to curb carbon emissions, a fully-fledged energy policy support scheme in this direction would require further, similar investigations and developments in the direction of households and transport. Putting in place forecasting models in all three energy categories (households, transport, and business/industry) is the first requirement to run so-called ensemble model counterfactuals, ending up with suggestions as to the most promising actions. As the word implies, action will require actionable features, such as taxes and/or efficiency.

Such prescriptive decision support, besides the forecasting, would also require the local energy system layout. Indeed, greenhouse gas emissions are not related only to energy consumption; more precisely, they are related to fossil-fuel-driven energy consumption. Thus, environmental taxes should take account of this layout and burden consumers according to the lifecycle emissions per consumed kWh.

5. Conclusion and ongoing work

This paper provides data and modelling insights into final energy and electricity consumption in the EU industrial sector, with the main and practical end-purpose being to develop mid-term energy planning and greenhouse gas reduction. All pertinent and available data from six countries from various parts of the EU have been collected and put together to develop the models.

We have attempted to introduce energy efficiency into the models, as encapsulated in the recently defined ODEX indicators. This indicator was found to be the most pertinent driver in the case of industrial energy. On the contrary, industrial demand, both final consumption and electricity, appeared to be price inelastic.

We are currently completing similar investigations for statistical and neural-network-based household and transport demand forecasting. We are introducing counterfactual analysis using the DiCE (Diverse Counterfactual Explanations) framework (Ramaravind et al., 2019) and look forward to bringing all our investigations together in an ensemble model counterfactual framework, where all actionable features can be tweaked to yield the required greenhouse gas reduction and design the appropriate policy action in any of the three key domains: industry, households, and transport.

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